

Review Article

Nigeria Upstream Petroleum Sector and Revenue Generation: The Moderating Role of Accounting Artificial Intelligence System

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Abstract

This paper has conceptually reviewed the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector and revenue generation with accounting artificial intelligence system as a moderating variable. An in-depth exploration of existing literature was made to buttress the views expressed by the researchers and prior research with regard to the subject matter examined. The study employs the desk-top review methodology by examining existing literature on the topic in order to get adequate firsthand information. Findings emanating from the conceptual review indicate that oil and gas serve as a major source of revenue for the Nigerian government, and as such, there should be adequate accountability for the number of barrels extracted from the upstream exploration. Based on this, the study suggested that the Nigerian government, policymakers, and upstream petroleum sector regulators should engage key players operating in the artificial intelligence and machine learning language industries to design and develop an accounting artificial intelligence solution system that will assist the upstream corporation in realising the actual volume of crude oil extracted and determining the actual revenue that is accrued to the revenue collection agencies without human disruption and manipulation on behalf of the Nigerian government.

Keywords: Accounting records machine intelligence, metering System, government revenue, Upstream petroleum.

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Introduction

One of Nigeria's most significant and valuable natural resources at the moment is petroleum products. There are two ways of financing government expenditure in Nigeria: through oil revenue and non-oil revenue. The Nigerian government sources a large proportion of its total revenue from petroleum income. It is utilised in a variety of ways to optimise its dividends for the country's growth and infrastructural development. Nigeria provides secure and enticing conditions to investors while also receiving a fair portion of the revenue made by the mining corporations (USEIA, 1997) as cited in Rotimi and Abdul-Azeez (2013). Nigeria is one of the top ten oil producers worldwide and among the largest in Africa, according to the Nigeria Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI) (2011), as cited in Rotimi and Abdul-Azeez (2013). However, the Nigeria's oil output increased by 91,476 barrels per day to reach 1,426,574 barrels daily in January 2024, compared to the production record of 1,335,098 bpd in December 2023, according to the most recent data from the Federal Government agency, the Nigeria Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission. (Nnodim, 2024). The Nigerian government is having a hard time dealing with the problems of low revenue and liquidity. The nation is rapidly implementing policies to combat the slump in the economy and looking into new revenue streams, particularly through the construction of infrastructure and the commercialization of the oil and gas sector. With the intentional introduction of an accounting system that will properly record, store, and document the quantity of crude oil per barrel extracted from the upstream through modern information technology such as an accounting artificial intelligence system, the huge sums of money lost to oil theft, bunkering, and undetected linkages by the Nigerian government can be minimised or eliminated from the upstream petroleum sector, which is the focus of this study.

After more than ten years of delay, the Nigerian National Assembly passed the Petroleum Industry Act 2021 (PIA), which seeks to overhaul the regulations and fiscal structure governing the operations of the oil and gas sector in Nigeria by transforming the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation into the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited, making it a commercial entity. The act further transformed the NNPC regulatory commissions into the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC) and the Midstream Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NMDPRC). This study focused on the upstream petroleum industry. The upstream petroleum sector plays a significant role in the development of oil-producing nations and is also a significant source of revenue generation for the government. As a result, it directly influences economic growth, particularly in emerging economies like Nigeria. Due to the huge need for petroleum resources, international oil market dynamics such as supply and demand are frequently influenced by the market price index. The upstream production sector provides the Nigerian government with a number of sources of revenue through exploration and field development, as well as the production and marketing of crude oil. The majority of nations typically use tools that are production-based or profit-based to collect the government's portion of economic rent and royalties (Emil et al., 2003). Government revenue generation in the form of royalties from oil extraction companies and sales of crude oil through the Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL) has not been able to demonstrate proper financial accountability because of human interference in the financial figures.

Onwughai (2022) stated that the accounting profession has undergone tremendous changes over the years, moving from regular, entirely human activities to automated computerised systems, resulting in a paradigm shift in the way the accounting profession is done with the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technology. According to Eleonora (2018), machine learning and deep learning are two examples of the areas of artificial intelligence that encompass any technology that allows computers to imitate human intelligence. It is the priority of this study to examine how the introduction of artificial intelligence into government revenue management can assist in curbing the fraudulent interference of government agency staff in charge of regulating, supervising, and overseeing the marketing of crude oil and natural gas to buyers on behalf of the Nigerian government in the upstream petroleum sector of the Nigerian oil and gas sector.

Statement of the Problem

The key operations that the Nigerian oil and gas sector is actively involved in are exploration, hydrocarbon production, refining, transportation, and marketing of crude oil and its refined products to the various users of these natural resources. There are two segments that make up the Nigerian oil industry: i) the midstream and downstream sectors, which involve refining, marketing, and distribution of refined products, as well as retailing. ii) The upstream sector, which involves exploration and field development, production, and marketing of crude oil. This study will focus on the upstream petroleum sector because of its major fiscal responsibility role as the bedrock for which government revenue is relied upon.

While the physical level of economic and social public investment on the ground does not commensurate with the amount of revenue receipts from the petroleum sector, successive government administrations have mainly underreported, recorded, and misused the oil revenue generated from the petroleum sector. Rotimi and Abdul-Azeez (2013) stated that public opinion also casts doubt on the veracity of payments made by oil firms to the Nigerian government in terms of taxes and royalties, among other things. This is further supported by the International Oil Companies' (IOCs) absence of accountability and openness when dealing with government officials in the petroleum industry. Also, Komolafe (2022) stated that the energy sector has been suffering from "crude oil theft," or the illicit access to crude oil and condensate by economic saboteurs, for more than a decade, especially in onshore and shallow sea terrains.

According to Yanling (2020), the integration and advancement of internet computing and artificial intelligence technology in the accounting profession have led to the predicted rise of artificial intelligence in accounting. Natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, robotics, machine learning, and speech recognition are some of the AI-related technologies that have made significant advancements over the years to create systems that act, reason, think, and constantly adapt faster ways of doing things. Interestingly, there has not been much research on the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector and revenue generation as it relates to the use of artificial intelligence technology in accounting. It is on this background that this study attempts to introduce another dimension of improving revenue accountability through artificial intelligence technology for the proper recording and summation of government revenue by examining the

moderating role of artificial intelligence on revenue generation and the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector. Recent studies by Danimir et al. (2019), Cocchi and Mazzeo (2020), Heimo and Othmar (2021), Mohammed and Shehu (2023) have acknowledged that artificial intelligence has a human-machine information processing system that can be used to assess accurate information in different fields of mankind.

Literature Review

The conceptual framework is illustrated on Figure 1 for the purpose of clarity and relationship.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Conceptual Review

Manasseh et al. (2022) stated that due to its essential usage in many aspects of daily life, crude oil has become a vital component of both developed and developing countries, making the oil and gas sector the economic powerhouse of most nations. Due to its extensive effects on the manufacturing of goods and the transportation system, among others, oil is immensely important.

With the advent of technology, there seems to have been a paradigm shift with the rise of digitization. Predictive analytics and the application of AI-based machine predictions have swiftly emerged as a result of easy access to new data sources, almost limitless computing capacity, and AI systems (Earley 2015; Mikalef et al., 2019). Using an efficient intelligent technology like AI to maximise cumulative extraction in the upstream hydrocarbon, ensuring transparency in data transmission, and reducing manipulation in hydrocarbon measurement is the simplest way to reduce fraudulent activities in terms of productivity and efficiency from crude oil revenue. For Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL) to have a better management process for keeping up-to-date accounting information, quick decisions must be made while keeping recurring difficulties in mind. In order to optimise the production and accounting processes in the oilfield, building a comprehensive accounting technological infrastructure through the

digitization of instrumentation equipment and the creation of network-based knowledge sharing is inevitable (Temizel et al., 2019).

It is clearly evident that digital technology has a significant impact on both society and business activities. The emergence of technologies that conflate the domains of the physical, digital, and biological spheres of human activities, such as artificial intelligence and robotics, has led to the perception of digital transformation as the "fourth industrial revolution" over time. Because of their strong generalisation capabilities and quick reaction times, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are garnering a lot of interest in many fields of human endeavour (Evans, 2019).

Revenue Generation

The majority of government revenue comes from crude oil, which has also been crucial in helping Nigeria's government pay for its expenditures. In Nigeria, oil accounts for around 90% of all exports and about 80% of government revenue, making it an important source of revenue for the Nigerian government (Omorie, 2019). According to Udo (2020), Nigeria's oil and gas sector generates significant amounts of petroleum revenue for the national treasury. These include sales of domestic crude oil, equity crude oil, gas, refined petroleum products, profits from NNPC subsidiaries, petroleum profits tax, company income tax, concession rentals, royalties from oil and gas, gas flare penalties, and other miscellaneous oil revenues. According to Rotimi and Abdul-Azeez (2013), in recent years, the oil sector has accounted for 40% of the Nigerian gross domestic product, 95% of export receipts, and over 80% of government revenue. About 15% of Nigeria's nominal GDP came from the crude oil industry between 2000 and 2009, demonstrating how reliant the country's economy is on these earnings. Additionally, the oil industry provides 70–75% of export earnings and around 50% of government revenue (Mehrara et al., 2010).

Following the announcement of the COVID-19 pandemic, the global gross domestic product of most nations significantly declined, and the impact on economic activity was negative worldwide, surpassing the predictions made by a report on energy and economic growth in 2020 (Manasseh et al., 2022). As a result, many economies were affected, particularly those in third-world nations like Nigeria. Nigeria, as a mono-economic nation, almost came to a complete halt as a result of the collapse of the price of crude oil, which fell from US\$58 per barrel in February 2020 to US\$32.29 per barrel in March 2020 and even further to US\$14 per barrel in April 2020 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022) 2020), as cited in Manasseh et al. (2022). Also, the ongoing Ukraine-Russian war has negatively affected the supply of oil in the international market, causing a decrease in the supply of oil. Furthermore, crude oil theft and oil bunkering are another menace facing the Nigerian oil and gas sector, with a negative impact on the nation's revenue. The issue of inefficient metering systems and a lack of transparency in storage tanks are additional challenges faced by the upstream sector. Many experts are concerned about the Nigerian economy's future because of the country's utter dependence on the hydrocarbon industry and its unstable nature.

According to Osiobe (2023), the implications of hydrocarbon accounting inaccuracies will include monetary losses, impaired regulatory compliance and transparency,

environmental harm, and decreased investment confidence. Therefore, now is the time for the Nigerian state to apply a more sophisticated information and communication technology like the accounting artificial intelligence machine automation system to determine the accurate hydrocarbon products extracted from the upstream petroleum sector and the equivalent revenue that is accrued to the Nigerian government in order to meet its numerous financial obligations and maintain a thriving economy, especially in light of the country's push towards a green economy. It is anticipated that net wealth will be generated due to Nigeria's substantial oil revenue, opening up greater opportunities for increasing domestic investment (Dauda et al., 2023).

Due to its vital role in many facets of our daily lives and the fact that the hydrocarbon sector is the engine room of most nations' economies, crude oil has become a vital resource for both established and emerging nations. Because of the extensive effects of the petroleum industry on the manufacturing of goods and the transportation system, this sector has become an extremely important area of concern. The price of crude oil is crucial to the growth of a nation, but the variations and volatility on the international market that cause changes to the global benchmark of oil price, either by increasing or decreasing, often have an impact on a number of economic developments. Most nations' economies heavily depend on the oil and gas sector for revenue generation and economic growth. With the current state of the Nigerian economy, understanding the details behind the transformation of a complex business process into an automated solution with the introduction of an accounting artificial intelligence solution software will be of tremendous benefit to the government in determining and collecting its actual revenue. The key players operating in the artificial intelligence and machine learning language industry, like IBM, Sufferscom Solutions, SparkCognition, C3.AI, Google Cloud, Microsoft Corporation, and Oracle, among others, can be contacted by the management of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation to design and develop an accounting artificial intelligence solution system that will assist the corporation in collecting the actual revenue that is accrued to the corporation without human disruption and manipulation.

The Upstream Petroleum Sector

Nigeria's most valuable and significant natural resource is petroleum. It is used in ways that maximise advantages to the nation's economy by giving investors secure and alluring terms in exchange for an appropriate proportion of earnings and economic rents. Petroleum is a significant source of foreign exchange for the producing countries, which is why it is crucial that this resource be appropriately valued in order to enable the governments and people of those countries to get the most out of their natural resources and maximise their advantages (2009, NEITI), as cited in Rotimi and Abdul-Azeez (2013). Nigeria's petroleum is categorised as "light" or "sweet" by the US EID, indicating that it is mainly sulphur-free. The upstream petroleum sector is responsible for the phases of operations in the oil and gas industry that include production and exploration work. To put it simply, exploration is the process of locating petroleum, while production is the process of making crude oil available. The exploration and production phases constitute the foundation of the oil and gas industry. As a result, the oil and gas value chain begin upstream. The Nigerian upstream petroleum sector market is mainly dominated by a government-owned company, the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited,

with joint ventures with private companies operating joint ventures and collaborations. The key players operating in this market include Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited, Royal Dutch Shell PLC, Chevron Corporation, ExxonMobil Corporation, and TotalEnergies SE.

The upstream petroleum sector remains Nigeria's most significant economic backbone, with which fiscal policy and the national budget are determined. Despite the consistent and increased pipeline vandalism on oil installations in most parts of the country where oil pipes are laid, notwithstanding the threat, the Nigeria upstream petroleum sector still remains the most reliable and dependable source of income for the government. Regardless of the country's ongoing problems of corruption, insecurity, and political instability, Nigeria's oil and gas sector still attracts major multinational oil companies, most of which are represented in Nigeria for the purpose of exploration and production (Mgbame et al., 2015).

The growing demand for oil and gas makes the discovery of new oil fields a high-priority need for companies in this sector of the Nigerian economy. The increase in demand for operations is generally referred to as exploration and production. Artificial intelligence has potential benefits for the oil and gas sectors in the areas of optimisation, exploration, and production processes (Bharadwaj, 2019).

The activity-based life cycle from the time an oil and gas field is legally acquired for exploration and development until it is legally abandoned includes the following: i) Exploration: This phase involves locating potential oil and gas deposits using technologies like seismic surveys and drilling well tools; ii) Appraisal: This phase's primary concern is the lowering of uncertainty and capital expenditure regarding the amount of hydrocarbons in the oil field; iii) Development: This phase entails planning the oil field, building production facilities, figuring out export procedures, and drilling the best wells to recover the reserves; iv) Production: During this stage, the wells' hydrocarbons are extracted; v) Abandonment: This stage occurs when the production operations are no longer profitable and all of the economic reserves have been removed from the field.

In the upstream petroleum sector, artificial intelligence and machine learning are being utilised for data analytics and interpretation to help predict future trends, account for actual revenue, find new reserves, and boost production in existing reserves. Global oil and gas companies are generally focused on applying artificial intelligence to streamline and simplify the exploration and production operations of the upstream petroleum sector. Upstream petroleum sectors can enhance their operations while coordinating their objectives with market trends with the use of digitalization, automation, and data analytics.

Big Data

Big Data analytics is a new technique that may be used to manage enormous datasets with the following six major features: complexity, value, veracity, volume, diversity, and velocity. The oil and gas sector has grown significantly in terms of data intensity with the introduction of data recording devices in exploration, drilling, and production activities.

Considering the volume of the raw data that forms the basis of information that is processed by the upstream sector of the Nigerian oil and gas industry, artificial intelligence will play a big role in assisting in the analysis of these data.

According to Mohammadpoor and Torabi (2018), there are several big data analytical tools and platforms that can assist AI in gathering, processing, analysing, and communicating. They include amongst others; i) Hadoop, which allows files to be split into large blocks and kept in distributed storage, ii) Mongo DB, which is used as a storage platform for real-time data like oil rigs deployed to oil exploration in the middle of the ocean, iii) Cassandra, which allows for the collection and storage of multiple data simultaneously from various sensors at different servers, iv) R programming, which facilitates complex statistical computation and also high-quality graphical output, v) Datameer, which has the capacity to integrate, analyse and visualize data regardless of structure, size and source, and iv) Big sheet, which is commonly used for refining, analysing, and visualization of large unstructured data like sales of the year by non-technical users in the oil and gas sector. These tools and platforms can be of tremendous assistance when synchronised into an accounting AI for the purpose of ensuring that the actual revenue accrued to the government of Nigeria is remitted after all the related costs of extraction and sales are deducted without human manipulation or interference.

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI), in all its integrated forms, from fuzzy logic to genetic optimisation to neural networks, has come a long way in recent years and is starting to gain traction in the oil and gas sector. It's becoming evident from recent advancements in the upstream oil and gas sector that the petroleum industry has grasped the enormous potential that artificial intelligence systems present (Cocchi & Mazzeo, 2020). To make the most use of the innovative hardware tools, an operative intermediary like artificial intelligence is needed to handle the software to process the data in real time in order to fully utilise these novel hardware instruments. The only practical methods for giving the new hardware real-time analysis and decision-making capabilities are systems that are intelligent, like artificial intelligence. Furthermore, a vast quantity of data, including critical and essential information such as the amount of crude oil extracted per day, is now accessible due to the introduction of new sensors that are permanently installed in the wellbore utilised by the upstream petroleum sector. Management of the upstream sector in Nigeria can utilise these sensors to determine the quantity of oil and gas extracted from the wellbore, considering any of the two basic methods for accounting for acquisition, exploration, development, and production costs in oil and gas exploration and production, viz., the successful efforts (SE) method and the full cost (FC) method.

Heimo and Othmar (2021) opined that digitalization has an effect on two very distinct areas of management accounting and the monitoring process. On one side is robotic process automation (RPA), which is the automation of repetitive, routine tasks, while on the other side is the support or automation of demanding analytical tasks (such as machine forecasts and artificial intelligence). While substantial progress is being made in automating regular activities, particularly in large companies, supporting analytical tasks appears to be much more challenging. Just 5% of German enterprises, according to a survey by the German Federal Ministry of Economy, presently employ AI in one of their

divisions (Feser, 2020). As a result, very few organisations use AI to regulate processes. Nonetheless, there are high hopes for the deployment of AI systems in the control and recording of financial transactions in the future (Seufert & Treitz, 2019).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the study of machines developed by humans that replicate human behaviour in operations, events, and activities. It is an ongoing effort to train the computer to learn, remember, think, and behave like humans. According to Shaffer et al. (2020), artificial intelligence (AI) is computer intelligence created by humans that can imitate logical processes and actions. They continued by defining artificial intelligence as the use of robotic technologies to solve issues that historically demanded human intervention. Danimir et al. (2019) claim that artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning will improve accountants' ability to obtain reliable, accurate, and timely information from a larger variety of sources. Eleonora (2018) predicted that AI will displace accountants in a lot of their more repetitive and regular tasks because it is clear that AI can complete more tasks faster and more accurately than humans.

Solanki et al. (2022) opined that there are two categories of artificial intelligence: weak and strong. An artificial intelligence system that is developed and created for a certain task is weak. When faced with an unusual solution, strong artificial intelligence is the system that, in the absence of human intervention, possesses generalised human consciousness. According to Rahmanifard and Plaksina (2019), particle swarm optimisation, fuzzy logic, genetic intelligence algorithms, and artificial neural networks are the four primary categories into which artificial intelligence techniques belong. These artificial intelligence techniques are very helpful in data analysis, record keeping, prediction processes, diagnostics, and the nonlinear complex transformation of information with a high degree of uncertainty, among others (Tapias et al., 2001).

Recent research and development indicate that artificial intelligence can enhance productivity and be beneficial across the board in the petroleum industry. With the rapid advancement in the technology of artificial neural networks and their methodology, which is grounded in the biological systems of humans, Artificial neural networks are utilised to generate hydrocarbons from shale reservoirs, estimate the bubble point pressure of crude oils, and assess the relative permeability of water to oil in reservoirs (Solanki et al., 2022). This same AI tool can be applicable to the accounting aspect of determining the input and output of oil and gas extraction and taking the total revenue and cost attached to each barrel of oil and gas in the upstream sector of the NNPC. The nonlinear model in artificial neural networks is a function that has a variable rate of change, meaning that the output changes by different amounts for different changes in the input. These can consist of well stimulation, infill drilling, and increased oil recovery. Genetic algorithms are problem-solving techniques that replicate the cognitive functions of humans to perform various duties. Genetic algorithms consist of initialization, assignment, selection, crossover, and mutation (Choubey & Karmakar, 2021).

Benefits of Artificial Intelligence in the Upstream Hydrocarbon Sector

1. Automated initial stages of exploration and production
2. Design artificial intelligence robots for ocean exploration.

3. Minimising the possibility of errors by substituting automated processes capable of duplicating the task for human operations.
4. Enhance natural oil detection capabilities.
5. Through artificial intelligence and machine learning, time-consuming tasks that are challenging for humans to do are replaced with time efficiency, such that thousands of contracts and extracting information can be completed within minutes.
6. Minimise operation cost and risk.
7. Streamline the supply chain.
8. Maximise return on investment on drilling costs
9. Artificial intelligence-based sensor learning in all oil fields to meet the requirements of sectorial development.
10. Increased production in oil exploration and development
11. Mobile integration to share updates with field workers

Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in the Nigerian Upstream Oil and Gas Sector

Artificial intelligence (AI) has had positive outcomes in numerous domains and has improved human lives (Zhang & Lu, 2021). According to Mohammed and Shehu (2023), artificial intelligence continues to show promise for improving human lives and advancing economies and civilizations in a number of areas, such as transportation, security, energy, and health. Nonetheless, artificial intelligence still has technological, social, ethical, and legal obstacles (Thiebes et al., 2021). Artificial intelligence has created potential in Nigeria to support sectors like health (Muhammad & Algehyne, 2021; Anazodo et al., 2022), security (Falode et al., 2021), education (Abayomi et al., 2021; Sanusi et al., 2022), and energy (Mobayo et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, a number of studies (Mobayo et al., 2021; Imhanyehor, 2021; Okwu 2021) point out a number of obstacles preventing the adoption of AI in Nigeria, including awareness, lack of system or field expertise, computing resources, obsolete cellular technology, outdated energy system facilities, increasing danger posed by cyber-attacks on devices, and AI system trust. With the right technical conditions, like explainable artificial intelligence, algorithms, and processing power, these shortcomings could be resolved. It is advantageous for these circumstances to improve in Nigeria in order to enhance AI performance and provide some level of explainability for AI decision systems, hence increasing the systems' reliability for use in the Nigerian upstream oil and gas sector.

Artificial Intelligence Methods of Accounting Systems in Petroleum Sector in Nigeria and its Application

The Nigerian petroleum industry may boost financial management, increase operational effectiveness, and make well-informed strategic decisions to promote growth and sustainability by utilising these AI accounting tools.

i. **Predictive Analytics Accounting Systems:** Predictive analytics software examines historical financial data to predict future trends and help decision-makers base their choices on facts. Predictive analytics can be utilised in Nigeria's petroleum industry to enhance budgeting and forecasting procedures, control risks, and optimise production planning.

ii **Machine Learning-Based Accounting Systems:** These tools can be used to classify transactions, automate data entry, and identify irregularities in financial data. Machine learning can assist Nigeria's petroleum industry in anticipating oil prices, allocating resources optimally, and increasing the precision of financial forecasts.

iii **Natural Language Processing Accounting Systems:** this system of AI can be used to increase stakeholder communication, streamline reporting procedures, and extract insights from unstructured financial documents in the petroleum sector. The natural language processing accounting system can help with textual data analysis from contract reports and regulatory papers in the Nigerian petroleum industry in order to extract important information for decision-making.

iv **Robotic Process Automation in Accounting System:** The robotic process automation technology can automate accounting tasks that are repetitive, like data entry, crude oil extraction metering records, reconciliation, and report preparation. Robotic process automation improves the efficiency and accuracy of financial processes in Nigeria's petroleum sector by streamlining inventory management, compliance reporting, and invoice processing.

Petroleum firms may increase financial transparency, boost operational efficiency, and gain a competitive edge in a dynamic and ever-changing market by implementing AI techniques into their accounting systems. In the changing petroleum industry, these AI-driven technologies help businesses make data-driven decisions, reduce risks, and achieve sustainable growth.

Accounting systems are undergoing a transformation because of AI techniques that automate tedious operations, analyse massive datasets, and offer insightful information for decision-making. Machine learning algorithms are highly accurate in classifying transactions, identifying abnormalities, and forecasting financial patterns. With the use of natural language processing, systems can converse more naturally with users and retrieve information from the point of oil extraction. Data entry and reconciliation procedures are streamlined by robotic process automation, which lowers errors and boosts productivity. All things considered, AI in accounting systems improves an organisation's ability to make strategic decisions, be it through increased accuracy, productivity, or both.

Accounting Records and Hydrocarbon Metering System

The introduction of digital technology like artificial intelligence in accounting for the purpose of determining the volume of crude oil extracted by multinational oil companies will be a welcome development in the Nigerian oil and gas sector and assist the country to tackle oil theft and inaccurate accounting of crude oil production. It will also enable the Ministry of Finance and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to know the actual output of oil extracted to get the equivalent amount in naira and dollars for proper accounting. Saudi Aramco and the Abu Dhabi National Oil Company (ADNOC) utilise digitally monitored oil installations in their nation in real-time. According to Okunloye (2023), inadequate measurement and metering accounted for around 40% of the crude oil lost in the Nigerian petroleum sector, rather than theft. This, he said, was found out as a consequence of a forensic analysis of oil theft data that the NUPRC conducted, which covered January 2020 to November 2022. Unachukwu (2023) described in detail the challenges experienced at several station points, such as wellhead/flow lines and central monitoring stations, highlighting the large revenue losses caused by obsolete manual logging, ineffective metering frameworks, unmetered flaring lines, and opaque storage tanks. Additionally, he noted that there was no metering at crucial locations such as custody transfer points, which resulted in over 40% of production losses, disagreements in data reconciliation, and problems meeting regulatory requirements.

Improper metering has made it difficult for the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector to record and account for the actual number of daily production barrels of crude oil per day and the revenue that is accrued to the government from their joint ventures, but with the adoption of an accounting artificial intelligence system, the Nigerian upstream sector will be able to account for the proper daily production barrels of crude oil per day and the revenue that is accrued to the government. The measurement of crude oil produced is done at the metering skid. According to Adekoya (2022), the current method utilised by the Nigerian government is to obtain daily production data from oil well operators in order to calculate the daily volume of crude oil extracted and determine oil revenues. This system would have resulted in billions of dollars lost as a result of inaccurate metering and dependence on oil company data. Furthermore, this would have resulted in the Nigerian government not knowing the actual daily oil production and would have created an avenue for most of the oil-producing companies to have been shortchanging the country for many years. This is like a man being a judge in his own case. Unachukwu (2023) suggested the implementation of cutting-edge technology, including multiphase flow metres, in-line metres, and automatic tank gauging systems, as well as single-point accountability for hydrocarbon accounting, as a recommendation for tackling the challenges of the proper hydrocarbon accounting system.

The joint venture companies are in charge of reporting the total number of crude oil production barrels per day. Since the revenue from exploration and production of crude oil is based on the volume of petroleum products extracted from a field, the quantity of crude oil extracted will determine how much money will be accrued to the government through the upstream petroleum sector. Knowing the quantity and measurement of crude oil extracted by multinational oil companies that are in joint venture with the upstream petroleum sector and keeping the actual accounting records is crucial for revenue purposes. Measurement is the process of figuring out the quantity and quality of

petroleum products that exist in an oil field (Oghenewede, 2020). Conversely, the quantity of petroleum product output plays a crucial role in determining the money received by the NNPC on behalf of the government and, to some extent, the economic feasibility of a given oil field. In particular, two types of measurement methods are used to determine the quantity of petroleum products: i) a measurement that is static, and ii) a dynamic measurement.

Methodology

The study employs a desktop review methodology to examine existing literature on the effect of Nigerian upstream petroleum sector on revenue generation with artificial intelligence as a moderator. This study identifies existing gaps, and made informed recommendation based on existing literature from other climes. Based on the review, conclusions were drawn and suitable recommendations were made with the intention of expanding the frontiers of knowledge on the influence of accounting artificial intelligence system as a moderating variable in the relationship between Nigeria upstream petroleum sector and revenue generation. This method was able to make the researcher access a wide range of information that are relevant, suitable and efficiently to the study. The scope of this study is the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector and the NNPC limited.

Conclusion

This study examines the moderating role of accounting artificial intelligence system on revenue generation and the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector. Artificial intelligence is a human-machine information processing system that can be used to assess accurate information in different fields of mankind. The use of an accounting artificial intelligence solution package based on existing literatures will enable government agencies in charge of crude oil metering know the total number of hydrocarbons extracted from the field. To improve efficiency, a number of Gulf-based oil and gas industries have started making additional investments in artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques are increasingly being used more often in the accounting systems of the petroleum industry in advanced economies to improve efficiency, enhance decision-making, and streamline procedures. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, including robotic process automation, natural language processing, and machine learning, are being used to analyse vast amounts of financial data, automate repetitive accounting operations, and spot irregularities or patterns that could point to possibilities or hazards. These AI tools can support regulatory compliance, resource allocation optimisation, and financial trend prediction. The integration of AI into the accounting systems of petroleum companies may increase corporate growth, gain important insights, make better financial decisions and increase sustainability, thereby reducing manual errors.

This study concludes that, if well implemented, artificial neural networks and machine learning languages have the potential to calculate the actual upstream petroleum sector's crude oil output, the actual revenue generated from the Nigerian oil and gas sector and the actual amount that is accrue to the Nigerian government.

Recommendations

The Nigerian government and policymakers through NUPRC and the management team of NNPC with their access to a wide range of monetary instruments to create a petroleum sector fiscal regime that would assure investment and guarantee an equitable revenue share should:

1. invite the key players operating in the artificial intelligence and machine learning language industry, like IBM, Sufferscom Solutions, SparkCognition, C3 AI, Google Cloud, Microsoft Corporation, and Oracle, among others, to design and develop an accounting artificial intelligence solution system that will assist the government agency in-charge of collection, collect the actual revenue that is accrued to the government without human disruption and manipulation.

2. ensure a concerted, intentional effort by the NNPC and security agencies to halt oil theft, pipeline vandalism, and oil bunkering.

3. ensure that the Nigerian National Assembly make laws that will declare any intentional improper measurement and metering a criminal offence.

4. make sure that the Nigerian Government sustain the kinetic approach utilised by the security forces in protecting the nation's petroleum assets.

5. make sure that there are severe consequences for staff of the NUPRC and NNPC that may compromise the regulatory policies for fraudulent reasons.

6. embark on technical training sessions on explainable artificial intelligence XAI constantly organised for staff of the revenue collection agencies to monitor the activities of the accounting artificial intelligence system.

Suggested Areas for Further Studies

Building on the insights gained from this review, there are several avenues for future studies that can deepen the understanding of Nigerian upstream petroleum sector and revenue generation: The moderating role of accounting artificial intelligence system. Some suggested areas for further research include:

- i. Auditing AI System: research can be conducted on the impact of Auditing AI system on the Nigerian upstream petroleum sector and revenue generation.

- ii. Chatbots: researchers can also conduct research to see how chatbots AI technology can instantly assist staff members of the Nigeria upstream petroleum sector and NNPC limited with accounting-related inquiries from the accounting AI system, thereby optimising internal procedures and enhancing productivity.

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